

RIG-I Activation and NKG2A Editing Synergize to Enhance NK Cell Antitumor Activity.

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Abstract

Background: Targeted innate immune activation and Natural Killer (NK) cell-based immunotherapies are both promising tools in cancer immunotherapy. Activation of the innate immune RNA sensor Retinoic acid-Inducible Gene-1 (RIG-I) has been shown to improve NK-cytotoxicity, but we observed that this effect varied significantly across tumor entities. We thus investigated potential inhibitors of RIG-I-induced NK-cytotoxicity as targets for CRISPR/Cas-mediated deletion for application in therapeutic NK cells in both Killer Ig-like Receptor (KIR)-matched and mismatched settings.

Methods: NK-cell cytotoxicity against common human tumor cell lines was investigated using a flow cytometry-based assay with and without prior RIG-I stimulation of tumor cells and NK cells. Publicly available array and RNAseq data were examined for potential RIG-I-induced inhibitors of NK cell cytotoxicity in tumor cells, which were then characterized using RT-PCR, immunoblotting and CRISPR/Cas genome editing. Subsequently, we developed a novel 2-guide CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing protocol for the deletion of NKG2A in primary NK cells and immortalized NK-92 cells for use in *in vitro* cytotoxicity models, including liver cholangiocarcinoma (CCC) organoids. CCC organoid culture was established from an intra-hepatic cholangiocarcinoma tumor resection specimen. KIR

expression and HLA/KIR status of NK cell donors were determined using sequence-specific PCR and high-resolution sequencing from genomic DNA.

Results: RIG-I induced HLA-E in all cell lines capable of surface HLA-E expression, and gene editing of HLA-E in tumor cells licensed RIG-I-mediated toxicity even in previously resistant cell lines, providing a rationale for the CRISPR/Cas-mediated deletion of the inhibitory HLA-E receptor NKG2A in NK cells. In combination, RIG-I activation in tumor cells and *NKG2A*-deletion in primary NK and NK-92 cells resulted in synergistically increased degranulation, IFN γ production and anti-tumor cytotoxicity. Importantly, in a CCC organoid model, *NKG2A*-deletion was critically required to license NK-cytotoxicity through RIG-I activation. This synergistic activity was observed regardless of KIR-match or mismatch status for all entities tested.

Conclusions: Our approach identified HLA-E as a critical inhibitor of RIG-I-mediated NK cell toxicity, with *NKG2A*-deletion reversing immune escape after RIG-I stimulation. Thus, as a combination therapy, *NKG2A*-deletion and RIG-I stimulation are a promising approach to improving NK-cell anti-tumor toxicity, with broad application to autologous and allogeneic NK-cell immunotherapy.

1 Introduction

2 Natural killer (NK) cell-based cancer immunotherapies have demonstrated both robust anti-tumor
3 activity and an excellent overall safety profile[1,2]. NK cells are cytotoxic innate lymphocytes, which
4 integrate multiple stress signals to recognize virally infected and malignantly transformed cells. Since
5 they act in antigen-agnostic manner and without HLA-restriction, NK cells can be applied as allogeneic
6 cell therapies and have intrinsic activity against a broad variety of tumor entities, limiting the
7 potential of tumor immune escape[1–3]. However, despite these key advantages, important
8 challenges to NK cell-based immunotherapies remain, including improving tumor cell recognition,
9 tumor penetration and cytotoxicity[2,4].
10 One important strategy in this regard has been the inhibition of NK cell immune checkpoints [5–7],
11 including classical immune checkpoints, such as programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1), TIGIT and
12 TIM3[6], as well as HLA-I specific inhibitory receptors. These inhibitory receptors can be broadly

13 divided into two categories (1) the inhibitory Killer Immunoglobulin Receptors (KIR), which are
14 relatively polymorphic and bind HLA-A, -B or -C molecules, with the exception of KIR2DL4, which
15 binds HLA-G, and (2) those of more limited polymorphism that bind non-classical HLA-I molecules.
16 These include ILT2, which is also activated by HLA-G, and the CD94-NKG2A heterodimer, which binds
17 HLA-E molecules presenting the leader sequences of HLA-A, B, C or G[8–10]. In addition to binding
18 the inhibitory receptor NKG2A, HLA-E also ligates the NK cell activating receptor NKG2C with broadly
19 overlapping peptide repertoires to NKG2A[9,11] although NKG2A demonstrates an overall higher
20 binding affinity[12–15] .

21 Approaches to circumvent both types of HLA-mediated NK cell inhibition are currently under clinical
22 investigation. KIR-mediated inhibition is avoided through the routine, intentional mismatch of donor
23 and patient KIRs during hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HCST) and NK cell-based
24 therapies[16–19] , which is done both in order to expand the donor pool and to potentially improve
25 anti-tumor cytotoxicity. In line with this, off-the-shelf NK-cell therapy using the immortalized NK
26 lymphoma cell line NK-92 has the advantage of low KIR expression overall[20]. Moreover, KIR
27 mismatch has been combined in therapeutic NK cells with multiple approaches targeting the
28 NKG2A/HLA-E inhibitory axis, including both blocking antibodies and genome editing of NKG2A[21–
29 24]. However, while phase 1 clinical trials with anti-NKG2A antibody blockade, alone and in
30 combination with anti-PD-L1 in solid tumors[25,26] have demonstrated the safety and tolerability of
31 this approach, the therapeutic benefit has been limited[25–27]. Moreover, there is evidence that
32 directly reducing NKG2A expression may prove more beneficial[22,28] , potentially due to increases
33 in NKG2C expression and activity[29] .

34 A different, yet promising, approach to improving anti-tumor immunity is the specific activation of
35 the anti-viral signaling receptors of the innate immune system[30,31], including the dsDNA sensor
36 cGAMP-synthase (cGAS) and the dsRNA receptors RIG-I and MDA5. All three receptors trigger upon
37 activation the release of type-I interferon (IFN) and other antiviral mediators[32] , and the underlying
38 principle of their application is to convert the tumor microenvironment (TME) from
39 immunosuppressive to immunogenic by mimicking an antiviral response, i.e. through the production

40 of chemokines, Th1-polarizing cytokines and boosting of antigen presentation[30]. Although ligands
41 for all three of these pathways are under clinical development as cancer immunotherapies[33,34],
42 multiple *in vitro* studies using human melanoma cell lines have demonstrated that RIG-I activation is
43 particularly advantageous for improving NK cell toxicity, both through its activation in tumor
44 cells[35,36] and effector cell-intrinsically in NK cells[37]. Moreover, several *in vivo* murine melanoma
45 studies using RIG-I activation have provided evidence that NK cell recruitment is essential to RIG-I-
46 mediated clearance[38,39], yet studies on NK cell activation in the context of other tumor entities
47 remain limited. Nonetheless, due to the exceptionally broad expression of RIG-I and its general
48 persistence in tumor cells when compared to cGAS/STING [40,41] and the existence of specific
49 agonists[42,43], RIG-I activation seems like a particularly promising approach to improving NK-cell
50 based therapies in general and particularly for adoptive NK cell approaches, although it has not yet
51 been investigated in this context.

52 In the following study, we systematically investigated the effect of tumor-cell specific and NK cell
53 specific RIG-I activation on NK-cytotoxicity, using IL-2/IL-15 *ex vivo* expanded primary NK cells and
54 NK-92, which are relevant models for NK-cell based therapies[20,44–47]. While we could not detect
55 additional cytotoxicity after NK-intrinsic RIG-I activation, RIG-I signaling in tumor cells did improve
56 NK-toxicity in many entities but not in all tumor cell types. Further investigation revealed that RIG-I
57 activation not only induced classical HLA-I upregulation but concurrently upregulated the NK cell
58 inhibitory ligand HLA-E. Moreover, deletion of the HLA-E gene using CRISPR/Cas9 licensed robust
59 RIG-I-mediated NK-cytotoxicity in previously non-responsive tumor cell lines, leading us to develop a
60 protocol for genome editing of the inhibitory HLA-E binding NKG2A receptor in primary NK cells.
61 Here, and in *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK-92 cells, we could observe that combined effect of NKG2A-deletion and
62 RIG-I activation led to substantially improved anti-tumor cytotoxicity, particularly in a
63 cholangiocarcinoma organoid model. Moreover, this improvement was independent of KIR ligand
64 matching or mismatching between NK donor and patient tumor cells. Altogether, the combination of
65 NKG2A editing and RIG-I activation is a promising approach to improving NK cell-based therapies and
66 is readily amenable to autologous and allogeneic applications.

67

68 **Results**

69 **RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity differs between tumor cell targets**

70 While a number of studies have investigated the effect of RIG-I activation on NK cell toxicity *in vivo*
71 and *in vitro* using the B16 murine melanoma model or human melanoma cells[36,37,39,48], specific
72 data on NK cell toxicity against other tumor entities after RIG-I stimulation remain limited, and, to
73 our knowledge, no study to date has investigated the effect of RIG-I stimulation on the cytotoxicity of
74 *ex vivo*-expanded primary NK cells or NK-92 cells, as utilized in NK-cell tumor immunotherapies. Thus,
75 we systematically investigated the effect of tumor-cell intrinsic and NK-cell intrinsic activation of RIG-
76 I on tumor cell cytotoxicity using *ex vivo* expanded NK cells and NK-92 cells cocultured with 10 widely
77 used tumor cell models[49–56] and two classical NK cell target cell lines K-562[57,58] and
78 721.221[57–60] (Fig.1, Sup. Fig. 1).

79 To investigate tumor cell-intrinsic RIG-I activation, tumor cells were stimulated with a short
80 5'triphosphorylated dsRNA (3p-dsRNA, specific RIG-I ligand)[42] or a control RNA (3p-ssRNA) and
81 subsequently cocultured with IL-2 and IL-15-expanded primary NK cells or NK-92 cells. NK-
82 cytotoxicity was assessed using flow cytometry[37,61] (Fig. 1a). As expected, prior stimulation of
83 tumor cells with a RIG-I agonist generally increased NK cytotoxicity[36,62]. However, the magnitude
84 of this effect varied greatly. While HT-29, SK-OV-3, A549, JEG-3, and U-2 OS showed increased
85 sensitivity towards primary NK-cell killing at almost all effector-to-target (E:T) ratios analyzed and
86 across donors, Capan-2, A-431, and PANC-1 showed significant NK-cytotoxicity increase only at the
87 highest E:T ratio (5:1)(Fig. 1b, Sup. Fig. 1a), and RIG-I stimulation of EFO-21, Caco-2, 721.221, and K-
88 562 had no significant effect on NK-cytotoxicity. We then investigated the effect of RIG-I stimulation
89 on cocultures with NK-92 (Fig. 1a, c), a cytotoxic natural killer cell line currently in use in clinical trials
90 for the treatment of diverse solid and hematological malignancies.[63,64] Here, we observed similar
91 effects: RIG-I stimulation induced higher NK-cytotoxicity towards Capan-2, A-431, HT-29, SK-OV-3,
92 PANC-1, A549, JEG-3, and U-2 OS cell lines at almost all E:T ratios, but only a slight tendency towards

93 increased killing was detected for EFO-21 (Fig. 1c, Sup. Fig. 1b). Moreover, no differences in
94 cytotoxicity were observed against Caco-2, 721.221, and K-562 cells after RIG-I activation.
95 Despite this substantial variability, only K-562 and 721.221 cells did not respond to RIG-I stimulation
96 with type I interferon (IFN-I) production, as quantified by HEK Blue IFN-I reporter cells (Fig. 1d, Sup.
97 Fig. 1c). Of note, no direct correlation was seen for the amount IFN-I production by target cells and
98 NK-cytotoxicity (Fig. 1e, Sup. Fig. 1d) nor was a pattern apparent for specific tumor entities, e.g. EFO-
99 21 and SK-OV-3 are both derived from ovarian serous cystadenocarcinoma, HT-29 and Caco-2 are
100 both derived from colon adenocarcinoma, yet these lines demonstrate differing susceptibilities to NK
101 cell cytotoxicity after RIG-I stimulation (Fig. 1e).

102 We then investigated a potential direct effect of cell-intrinsic RIG-I stimulation in the NK cells by
103 stimulating cultured, primary NK and NK-92 cells with 3p-dsRNA or non-stimulatory 3p-ssRNA control
104 prior to tumor cell coculture (Sup. Fig. 1e-g). Here, however, we detected no differences in
105 cytotoxicity after direct RIG-I activation in either of these NK cell models (Sup. Fig. 1f, g). These data
106 differ substantially from what we have observed for freshly isolated, primary NK cells, which
107 demonstrated higher toxicity against melanoma or during influenza virus infection after direct, cell-
108 intrinsic RIG-I activation[36,65,66], with this difference likely resulting from changes in the NK cells
109 during culture and/or expansion.

110 **The MHC-I molecule HLA-E is broadly upregulated by RIG-I stimulation.**

111 We then attempted to characterize what processes might limit NK cell cytotoxicity against tumor
112 cells despite intact RIG-I antiviral signaling (Fig. 1d). Analysis of published transcriptional data in the
113 Gene Expression Omnibus database showed that RIG-I stimulation on tumor cell lines not only
114 enriched antiviral signaling pathways but also those that conferred protection from NK
115 cytotoxicity[67–69]. Functional enrichment analysis identified the pathway ‘GO:0042270, Protection
116 from Natural Killer cell mediated cytotoxicity’, and, from this set, we could observe upregulation of
117 the HLA class I molecules, specifically HLA-A, HLA-B, HLA-E, and HLA-G, across all three analyzed
118 studies (Fig. 2a). In addition to GO:0042270, we also investigated programmed cell death ligand 1
119 (PD-L1) expression, as it has been shown that RIG-I promoted immune evasion in colon cancer by

120 upregulating this axis on HT-29 cells.[70] However, analysis of our *ex vivo* expanded NK cells and NK-
121 92 cells showed only marginal levels of PD-1 expression, excluding PD-L1 as a mediator of tumor cell
122 protection in our model (Sup. Fig. 2a). In line with this, we observed that HT-29 cells were readily
123 susceptible to RIG-I mediated NK-cytotoxicity (Fig. 1b), unlike what has been previously reported for
124 T-cell cytotoxicity[70] .

125 The ability of RIG-I to upregulate MHC-I/HLA-I molecules in murine and human melanoma models is
126 well characterized[39,71]. Similarly, in the diverse tumor cell lines we investigated, we could also
127 observe upregulation of the classical HLA-A/B/C molecules 1 and 2 days after RIG-I activation or IFN γ
128 stimulation via flow cytometry (Fig. 2b), with the exception of 721.221 and K-562 cells, which are
129 both widely used as NK feeder/target cells due to their lack of classical HLA-I molecules on their
130 surface.[57,59,60,72,73] Nonetheless, it should be noted that, while classical HLA-I molecules are
131 highly polymorphic, the NK cell toxicity observed in these tumor cell lines after RIG-I stimulation did
132 not demonstrate any form of donor specificity (Fig. 1, Sup. Fig. 1). Thus, the pattern observed in
133 Figure 1 was not indicative of classical HLA/KIR-mediated NK cell inhibition. In contrast, the non-
134 classical HLA molecules, HLA-E and HLA-G, have limited polymorphism[74,75] and thus were more
135 promising candidates.

136 We measured HLA-G expression on all cell lines by immunoblotting. As previously reported, we could
137 observe extremely high HLA-G expression on the choriocarcinoma cell line JEG-3[76] (Fig. 2c) and
138 lower levels on the ovarian carcinoma line SK-OV-3[77] (Sup. Fig. 2b). We then investigated the effect
139 of RIG-I stimulation on HLA-G levels. Here, 3p-dsRNA induced HLA-G mRNA expression in SK-OV-3, A-
140 431, and A549 cells, while HLA-G mRNA levels remained high but unaltered in JEG-3 (Fig. 2d).
141 However, at the protein level, this induction could only be observed in SK-OV-3 (Sup. Fig. 2c). Thus,
142 due to its limited expression at the protein level, we could exclude HLA-G as a common mediator of
143 NK cell evasion in our model.

144 We then investigated HLA-E expression by immunoblotting and could observe a readily detectable
145 baseline expression in all cell lines tested (Fig. 2e). We then analyzed the regulation of HLA-E at the
146 mRNA level after RIG-I activation but also in response to other nucleic acid sensing pathways of the

147 innate immune system (Fig. 2f, g, Sup. Fig. 2d, e). Here, induction of the interferon-stimulated gene
148 IFIT1 and the chemokine CXCL10 were measured to test the functionality of each signaling
149 pathway[78,79], and the control stimuli IFN α and IFN γ , which are known to induce IFIT1 (IFN α >IFN γ),
150 CXCL10 (IFN γ > IFN α) and HLA-E (IFN γ)[80,81], were used to test type I and II IFN signaling in all cell
151 types. The responses to type I and II IFN stimulation were as expected in all cell lines except for
152 721.221, which was unresponsive to IFN γ stimulation and only demonstrated a limited response to
153 IFN α . In line with Fig. 1d, robust RIG-I signaling was again present in 10 of the 12 cell lines tested.
154 Moreover, a slight IFIT1 response to RIG-I stimulation was detected in 721.221 cells, which was likely
155 under the threshold of the IFN activity assay in Sup. Fig. 1c. In all 10 cell types with a robust RIG-I
156 response, induction of HLA-E mRNA could also be observed. However, for the other nucleic acid
157 sensors, the induction of HLA-E was less consistent overall. Eight of the tested cell lines
158 demonstrated functional cGAS-STING signaling after dsDNA stimulation (A-431, A549, Capan-2, EFO-
159 21, HT-29, JEG-3, PANC-1, and SK-OV-3). However, of these, SK-OV-3 and A-431 did not demonstrate
160 significant HLA-E induction. Among the cells with a functional TLR3 response (A-431, A549, Capan-2,
161 SK-OV-3, and HT-29), only A-431 showed increased HLA-E mRNA after stimulation with non-
162 transfected poly(I:C). Cytosolically transfected poly(I:C) was used to test MDA5 responses, which
163 could be observed in A-431, A549, Capan-2, EFO-21, HT-29, JEG-3, PANC-1, SK-OV-3, and U-2 OS, but,
164 surprisingly, only A549 demonstrated significant upregulation of HLA-E after MDA5 activation. Thus,
165 RIG-I activation seemed to have a unique ability to upregulate HLA-E mRNA expression in diverse
166 tumor cell types.

167 In order to mimic tumor cell stimulation over time, we investigated HLA-E regulation at the protein
168 level 1 or 2 days after stimulation with IFN γ or 3p-dsRNA (Fig. 2h, Sup. Fig. 2f, g). Here, we could
169 observe an increase of HLA-E protein levels by immunoblotting (Sup. Fig. 2f) and flow cytometry,
170 both intracellularly (Sup. Fig. 2g) and at the cell surface (Fig. 2h), as is required for NKG2A and NKG2C
171 receptor interaction. Notably, we did observe that the commonly used NK cell targets 721.221 and K-
172 562 express HLA-E as previously reported[82], yet our data indicate that they do so overwhelmingly
173 intracellularly, with less than 2% of the cells being HLA-E positive by surface staining, in line with the

174 lack of classical HLA-I expression in these cell lines[72,74]. Thus, even after treatment with IFN γ (Sup.
175 Fig. 2g), the HLA-E expressed by these K-562 or 721.221 cannot effectively interact with NKG2A and
176 inhibit NK-cytotoxicity, a feature which doubtlessly contributes to their particular vulnerability to NK-
177 cytotoxicity.

178 **HLA-E induction on tumor cells limits RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity.**

179 The HLA-E:CD94-NKG2A immune checkpoint has been the subject of intense translational
180 research[83–85] and is currently under investigation in multiple clinical trials (NCT03822351,
181 NCT05221840, NCT03794544, NCT05061550, Reviewed in [86]). However, no study to date has
182 explored the effect of innate immune stimulation on this axis. Thus, we generated *HLA-E*^{-/-} A-431,
183 A549, Caco-2, EFO-21, and SK-OV-3 cells using CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing (Sup. Fig. 3a, b, Sup.
184 Table 1) and investigated NK-mediated cytotoxicity in combination with RIG-I and IFN γ stimulation.
185 In general, *HLA-E*^{-/-} clones were lysed more efficiently by primary NK cells (Fig. 3a, Sup. Fig. 3c), in line
186 with a previous report[87], and we could observe a similar effect for NK-92 cells (Fig. 3b, Sup. Fig.
187 3d). Following 3p-dsRNA stimulation of tumor cells, we observed a robust increase in cell-surface
188 HLA-E expression (Sup. Fig. 3b) and an increase in NK-cytotoxicity in SK-OV-3 and A-549 cells, even at
189 low E:T ratios (Fig. 3a, b, Sup. Fig. 3 c, d, g), as in our previous data (Fig.1b, Fig. 2h, Sup. Fig. 1a).
190 However, in all cell lines, even at extremely low E:T ratios (0.6:1), the combination of RIG-I
191 stimulation and HLA-E deficiency either enabled or enhanced cytotoxicity in a synergistic fashion in
192 both primary NK cells and NK-92 cells (Fig. 3a-d Sup. Fig. 3c-h). In particular, HLA-E deficiency was
193 critically required for RIG-I induced cytotoxicity against EFO-21, A-431 and Caco-2 cells at low E:T (Fig.
194 3c, d, Sup. Fig. 3e,f) and, against A-549, RIG-I stimulation was required to enable the cytotoxic effect
195 of HLA-E deletion (Sup. Fig. 3 g, h).

196 We also investigated IFN γ pretreatment since this robustly induced HLA-E expression (Fig. 2f-h, Sup.
197 Fig. 3i) and has been applied in other studies involving the NKG2A/HLA-E axis[23,24] . In contrast to
198 RIG-I, IFN γ pretreatment of the target tumor cells led to a significant decrease in NK cytotoxicity in
199 numerous cell lines (Fig. 3e, f, Sup. Fig. 3j, k). However, deletion of HLA-E abrogated this inhibitory
200 effect. IFN γ had a neutral, rather than a negative effect, on primary NK-cytotoxicity in cocultures with

201 *HLA-E*^{-/-} A-431 or A549 cells, and IFN γ pretreatment even increased killing for *HLA-E*^{-/-} SK-OV-3 (Fig.
202 3e). This effect was even stronger in NK-92 cells (Fig. 3f), with HLA-E deletion restoring cytotoxicity
203 after IFN γ stimulation for all cell lines (Fig. 3f), confirming HLA-E as a key suppressor of NK-mediated
204 killing after IFN γ exposure, an inevitable consequence of tumor cell proximity to activated NK cells.
205 Of note, no differences were observed for K-562 and 721.221 (Sup. Fig. 3l, m), in line with their
206 limited responses to IFN γ (Fig. 2g) and their predominantly intracellular expression of HLA-E (Sup. Fig.
207 2h).

208 Overall, there are 17 known alleles of HLA-E with the potential to differentially modulate NK cell
209 signaling[88] . However, the combined frequency of the two most common HLA-E alleles E*01:01
210 and E*01:03 is reported to be about 0.99[89] . Thus, we also decided to analyze the effect of these
211 two alleles on NK-cytotoxicity using two lentiviral overexpression systems in A-431, A549, SK-OV-3,
212 and HT-29 (Fig. 3g, Sup. Fig. 3n-p). Here, we observed a higher surface expression of the 01:03 allele
213 in all four cell lines as previously described[90] (Sup. Fig. 3n). Nonetheless, both alleles demonstrated
214 inhibitory effects on NK-mediated lysis when cocultured with primary NK cells (Fig. 3g, Sup. Fig. 3o),
215 and NK-92 cells (Sup. Fig. 3p), indicating that induction of both of these HLA-E alleles by RIG-I could
216 act as an NK cell inhibitory factor in a large proportion of the population.

217 **Paired guide RNA CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing enables NKG2A deletion in primary NK cells.**

218 While the genetic modification of patient-derived tumor cells is a feasible technique *in vitro*, it is not
219 suitable for clinical settings. Instead, clinical development has focused on approaches targeting the
220 inhibitory HLA-E receptor NKG2A with blocking antibodies or by inhibiting NKG2A expression[21–
221 24,27]. While anti-NKG2A targeting antibodies have demonstrated limited effectivity in clinical
222 trials[25–27], two studies have provided evidence that directly targeting NKG2A expression on NK
223 cells may induce more NK-cytotoxicity than antibody blockade[22,28], potentially due to an increase
224 in expression and activity of NKG2C[29] .

225 We thus investigated approaches to generating efficient bulk frameshift mutations targeting NKG2A
226 in primary NK cells using CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing. Based on previous CRISPR editing approaches
227 targeting lncRNAs in immortalized cell lines[91,92] , we electroporated primary NK cells with

228 ribonucleoproteins containing one or two gRNA(s) in combination (Fig. 4a,b, Sup. Fig. 4a-g). Using
229 Sanger sequencing and indel analysis with the TIDE package[93] in R, we observed that combined
230 gRNA electroporation led to a substantially higher proportion of statistically significant frameshifts
231 (Fig. 4b): 47.5% for guide1, 0% for guide2, and 65% for the paired guides, or 0% for guide 3 and
232 20.67% for guide 4, and 39.3% for their combination). Moreover, for paired guides (#1+#2), we
233 observed a high proportion of sequences presenting with a larger deletion in their locus equal to the
234 distance between the two gRNA complementary sequences, which was readily visible in gel
235 electrophoresis (Sup.Fig.4b, c), with some donor variation but reaching in some cases nearly 70% of
236 the reads (Sup. Fig. 4d-g). The exact determination of the proportion of edited alleles was
237 confounded by a high number of unassignable reads (N.A., Fig. 4b), as observed in another study[23].
238 However, analysis of cell-surface expression of the NKG2A protein revealed much clearer and more
239 robust results (Fig. 4c). Here, the combination of gRNA #1+#2 lead to a (93.2%-26.7% =) 66.7% and
240 decrease in NKG2A+ cells overall, a far more efficient result than previously indicated by genome
241 sequencing. Similarly, the combination of gRNA #3+#4 resulted in a 49.5% decrease. These results at
242 the protein level indicated higher genome editing efficiency than any of the other published studies
243 on NKG2A-editing to date[23,24,28,29,94] without the additional use of cell sorting. Due to the high
244 efficiency that we could achieve in primary NK cells, we thus decided to follow this paired guide
245 approach with gRNA #1+#2 for the generation of NKG2A^{-/-} cells in this study (Fig. 4b).

246 We then analyzed the phenotypes of the primary NK populations electroporated either with the two
247 gRNAs targeting NKG2A (NKG2Ag), or one control guide (-CTRg) using flow cytometry and ELISA (Fig.
248 4d-f, Sup. Fig. 4h, i). Using the paired gRNA approach with a 70% reduction in NKG2A-expressing cells
249 (Fig. 4d), we observed a concurrent increase in the proportion of NKG2C-expressing cells (17% for -
250 CTRg vs 23% for NKG2Ag), in line with a previous report[29], although to a lower extent than
251 observed there (68.0% in WT NK cells vs 97.6% NKG2A-KO NK cells). Moreover, in contrast to their
252 study, we did not observe an increase in KIR2D expression. Beyond this, no differences in NKG2D,
253 KIR2D, CD8, NKp30 or NKp44 expression were observed when compared to the -CTRg paired donors
254 (Fig. 4d). Upon activation with 721.221 target cells, we did detect a small but significant increase (4.7

255 %) in the degranulation marker LAMP1/CD107a on the surface, indicative of higher activation of the
256 NK cells by the target cells, but no differences in other activation markers, such as CD69 or the
257 costimulatory molecule CD137, or in levels of effector molecules like Granzyme B, Perforin, or IFN γ
258 and TNF α cytokines (Fig. 4e). While the reduction of NKG2A only modestly impacted the activation of
259 the NK cells cocultured with 721.221, in line with its minimal HLA-E surface levels (Fig. 2h), analysis of
260 NK-cytotoxicity of cocultures with cell lines expressing considerably higher surface levels of HLA-E,
261 including A-431, A549 and Capan-2 revealed significantly higher NK-cytotoxicity for NKG2A Δ cells (Fig.
262 4f, Sup. Fig. 4i, j), in line with other reports[29,95]. Furthermore, we also observed higher levels of
263 IFN γ production (Fig. 4g, Sup. Fig. 4k). As demonstrated in a previous study[23], further sorting to
264 obtain a relatively pure NKG2A Δ population did not further improve NK cell toxicity (data not shown),
265 so we opted to use unsorted bulk NKG2A-edited cells in our further experiments.

266 We also generated *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK-92 cells (Sup. Fig. 4l), with which we observed similar results in
267 cocultures with the NK-92 cell line (Sup. Fig. 4m, n), indicating that NKG2A deletion could potentially
268 be applied to NK-92-based NK cell therapies, which has not been done to date.

269 **NKG2A-edited primary NK and NK-92 cells act synergistically with RIG-I stimulation to promote**
270 **anti-tumor toxicity.**

271 We then combined NKG2A deletion in NK cells and RIG-I stimulation in tumor cells and assessed their
272 combined cytotoxicity. As expected, RIG-I activation with 3p-dsRNA increased HLA-E levels in all cell
273 lines test (Sup. Fig. 5a). Moreover, in the control conditions (-CTRg), it enhanced primary NK-
274 cytotoxicity against the A-431 and Capan-2 cell lines (Sup. Fig. 5b) cells but not cocultures with EFO21
275 or Caco-2 cells (Fig. 5a). However, after combining these approaches (NKG2A Δ , 3p-dsRNA), a
276 synergistic enhancement of NK cell-mediated killing could be seen in all four cell lines (Fig. 5a, b, Sup.
277 Fig. 5b, c). In particular, Caco-2 and EFO21 cells critically required NKG2A deletion was to license RIG-
278 I mediating killing in these lines. This approach could also be applied to NK-92 cells (Sup. Fig. 5d),
279 with *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK-92 cells also demonstrating synergistic NK-cytotoxicity against all four cell lines (Fig.
280 5c, d, Sup. Fig. 5e, f).

281 We then investigated the potential of this combined immunotherapy in a patient-derived solid tumor
282 organoid model, where RIG-I could be particularly beneficial to improving immune cell
283 infiltration[30,96] . We tested patient-derived liver cholangiocarcinoma (CCC) organoids (Fig. 5e-h)
284 from a male patient of 63 years, who suffered from a grade 2 primary intrahepatic
285 cholangiocarcinoma, which was positive for cytokeratin 7 (CK7) and negative for CA19-9 . This
286 histology could also be confirmed in organoid cultures by immunohistochemistry (Fig. 5e). We
287 cocultured these organoids with primary NK cells with and without NKG2A deletion and with and
288 without RIG-I activation. Here, although RIG-I stimulation did increase HLA-E expression in the
289 organoid cells (Fig. 5f), it did not increase NK-cytotoxicity against the organoid when used alone (Fig.
290 5g, h). In contrast, NKG2A deletion on NK cells did increase NK-cytotoxicity, and an even stronger,
291 synergistic increase in cytotoxicity could be observed for the combination of NKG2Ag NK cells and
292 RIG-I activation (Fig 5g, h). Thus, in CCC organoids, NKG2A-deletion was again critically required to
293 license RIG-I stimulation to further enhance anti-tumor cytotoxicity, providing an important rationale
294 for the combination of these approaches in solid tumors.

295 **Synergistic cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited NK cells and RIG-I stimulation is independent of**
296 **donor/tumor KIR-matching.**

297 Killer Immunoglobulin-like Receptor (KIR) mismatch (MM) has demonstrated significant potential for
298 enhancing the efficacy of allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation during the treatment of
299 hematological malignancies[17,97,98]. Although allogeneic NK-cell-based therapies including KIR
300 mismatching are currently under investigation in a number of clinical trials[18,19,47] , no head-to-
301 head comparison of KIR matching and mismatching has been undertaken to date, although the
302 general assumption in the field is that KIR mismatching would benefit the availability and effectivity
303 of NK-cell based tumor immunotherapies [17,99,100].

304 Since RIG-I stimulated cells showed increased expression of all HLA-I and not only HLA-E (Fig. 2a, b),
305 we decided to test whether the KIR-matching state of the NK donors influenced the effect of
306 combined NKG2A deletion and RIG-I treatment on their cytotoxicity. To determine matches and
307 mismatches, we used what is known as a *KIR receptor-ligand*[100] or *missing ligand*[99] model. To

308 this end, we genotyped the HLA class I and KIR genes in our NK donors and compared them to the
309 annotated HLA-I ligands expressed on standard tumor cell lines (Fig. 6a). For a particular tumor cell
310 line, we defined *KIR-matched* NK cells as those coming from a donor who (1) expressed the KIRs
311 recognizing the HLA-I ligands expressed on the tumor cell line, (2) also expressed the HLA-I ligands
312 for these KIRs so that they were activated during the licensing of NK cells in the donor, (3) did not
313 express KIR/HLA combinations that are not found on the cell line (Fig. 6a). A KIR mismatch (KIR MM)
314 was defined as NK cells from a donor who expresses at least 2 KIR/cognate HLA combinations for
315 which the ligands are missing on the tumor cell line (Fig. 6a).

316 We then selected NK donors with KIR ligand-receptor matching and mismatching for Capan-2, A-431
317 and A549 cells (Sup. Table 2) for NK-cytotoxicity assays with NKG2A deletion (Fig. 6b, Sup. Fig. 6a).
318 Here, we observed that NKG2A reduction on NK cells led to higher cytotoxicity regardless of the KIR-
319 matching state (Fig. 6b). Of note, we also measured a small but significant increase on KIR2DL3 (and
320 possibly KIR2DL2) on the surface of NKG2A edited cells when measured by flow cytometry (Sup. Fig.
321 6b), but this seemed to have little impact on the cytotoxicity overall, although the target cells all
322 express HLA-C1 molecules. Of note, when we compared the cytotoxicity of the -CTR populations with
323 each other, we also observed a tendency towards more killing of A549 and Capan-2 for KIR MM, but
324 not for A-431 (Sup. Fig. 6c). Beyond this, we also defined and evaluated the effect of a partial KIR
325 mismatches, in which both KIRs necessary for mismatch were present on the NK donor, but only one
326 of the HLA-I ligands was present on the same donor (Sup. Fig 6d, e). In this context, we observed that
327 a single KIR3DL1 mismatch in A-431 cells surprisingly enhanced cytotoxicity (Sup. Fig. 6e). Conversely,
328 KIR2DL1 mismatch in A549 and Capan-2 appeared to have a less pronounced effect, showing a slight
329 tendency to increase cytotoxicity in A549, while remaining unchanged in Capan-2.

330 We then applied the combination of RIG-I stimulation on the target cells and NKG2A CRISPR editing
331 of the NK cells to settings with KIR ligand-receptor matching and mismatching (Fig. 6c, Sup. Fig. 6f, g).
332 Strikingly, our data revealed comparable increases in cytotoxicity due to RIG-I stimulation when using
333 both KIR-matching and KIR-mismatching NK cells, as well as for CRISPR/Cas9 mediated ablation of
334 NKG2A. Additionally, a similar enhancement in cytotoxicity was noted with the combined application

335 of NKG2A-deletion in the NK cells and RIG-I stimulation of the targets. Overall, these results
336 demonstrate their cooperative effect on NK cytotoxicity independently of the KIR ligand-receptor
337 combination expressed on the NK and target cells (Fig. 6c). Of note, the NKG2A reduction achieved
338 using CRISPR/Cas9, although varying with each donor, was comparable among NK with matching and
339 mismatching KIRs for the same target (Sup. Fig. 6f, g).

340 Altogether, these data demonstrate the compatibility of NKG2Ag and RIG-I activation with both
341 autologous and allogeneic NK cell-based therapies, thus widening their potential application to
342 potential off-the-shelf NK cell-therapeutic approaches.

343 **Discussion**

344 NK cell-based immunotherapies harbor great clinical promise but still face important hurdles in their
345 broader application. Much like the currently approved CAR T cell therapies, current CAR NK cell
346 approaches overwhelmingly target the hematopoietic compartment[101], which is easier to target
347 both due to tumor cell accessibility and the clinical feasibility of concurrent depletion of non-tumor
348 cells using targets such as CD-19, BCMA and CD33[46,102] . To improve potential applications of NK-
349 cell based therapies to solid tumors, with or without CAR expression, NK cell therapies will need
350 improved tumor penetration, cytotoxicity and overall recognition of malignantly transformed cells[1–
351 3] .

352 In our study, we have combined two approaches to improving anti-tumor NK-toxicity: (1) genome
353 editing of NKG2A on NK cells and (2) activation of the innate immune RNA receptor RIG-I in tumor
354 cells. Although we and others have previously investigated the effect of RIG-I activation on NK-
355 cytotoxicity, most studies have been performed with fresh, primary NK cells and using human or
356 murine melanoma cell lines. However, due to the translational nature of the present study, we chose
357 to investigate a broad number of tumor cell lines from different entities and utilize *ex vivo* expanded
358 NK cells and the clinically relevant immortalized NK-cell line, NK-92[20,44,45] . Here, we observed
359 key differences to our previous studies (Fig. 1)[36,37,66]: (1) in the NK cell types we used here, we
360 could not detect any increase in NK-cytotoxicity after NK cell-intrinsic RIG-I activation (Sup. Fig. 1e-g),
361 and (2) after tumor cell-intrinsic RIG-I activation, the resultant NK-cytotoxicity varied considerably,

362 ranging from high to non-existent. The former point is likely due to the difference in culture
363 conditions. While our previous studies used fresh NK cells, the *ex vivo* expansion protocol for primary
364 NK cells and NK92 cells uses IL-2 and IL-15 for weeks in culture, also resulting in chronic exposure to
365 IFN γ and other proinflammatory cytokines released by the proliferating NK cells. These factors
366 preactivate the NK cells[103–106], and, while this leads to better anti-tumor toxicity overall, it may
367 also render additional RIG-I activation superfluous. The latter difference is likely due to the massive
368 variation in NK-cell susceptibility and HLA-E expression and induction between different tumor cell
369 types. Here, it should be noted that while RIG-I activation has proven beneficial in models of
370 melanoma, pancreatic cancer and AML[38,107,108] , it has also been shown to promote immune
371 escape and tumor development in models of colon carcinoma and breast cancer[70,109] . Since both
372 of these critical studies demonstrated induction of PD-L1 on tumor cells, and, in line with this, our
373 study observes upregulation of the inhibitory checkpoint ligand HLA-E, it seems clear that RIG-I
374 mediated tumor immunotherapy would greatly benefit from T cell and/or NK cell checkpoint
375 inhibition for many entities, perhaps in combination, in line with other studies on PD1-checkpoint
376 inhibition[110,111] . Beyond this study, which specifically investigates the utility of combining
377 NKG2A-deletion and RIG-I activation in the context of NK-cell therapy, our data also indicate a
378 potential synergy for RIG-I activation and NKG2A-blockage, e.g. through monoclonal antibodies,
379 during tumor immunotherapy approaches without adoptive cell transfer, as well.

380 While it was our own investigation of the tumor cell lines that we utilized that lead us to identify
381 HLA-E/NKG2A as a key inhibitory axis limiting RIG-I mediated NK-cytotoxicity (Fig. 2, 3), NKG2A
382 inhibition has been the subject of intense translational research[27,112,113] . Nonetheless, our study
383 is the first to investigate NKG2A in the clinically relevant NK cell line NK-92 and the first to combine
384 the inhibition of this checkpoint with innate immune stimulation and thus to demonstrate their
385 synergistic contribution to tumor-cell clearance. Given the overall weaker cytotoxicity of NK-92,
386 combinatorial approaches to augment its efficacy have great potential, in particular in creating
387 affordable, readily expandable off-the-shelf therapies for a broader population in need of cellular
388 therapies.

389 Moreover, while we have used the transfection of specific RIG-I ligands to activate antiviral sensing,
390 such a combinatorial approach could doubtlessly be extended to other approaches that activate
391 antiviral immunity, including oncolytic viruses, chemotherapy and irradiation[114,115]. Similarly,
392 IFN γ , a key NK cell cytokine, generally expected to strengthen immune effector function, actually
393 limited NK-cytotoxicity in our experiments in an HLA-E dependent manner (Fig. 3), and our data
394 indicate that HLA-E (and HLA-G) induction by IFN γ likely contribute to its ambiguous role in anti-
395 tumor immunity[116,117]. Furthermore, these results highlight the potential benefit of combining
396 NKG2A-deletion with CAR-NK cell approaches, as used in a very recent study combining NKG2A
397 editing with an anti-CD33 CAR directed against AML [24].

398 Overall, the synergistic effect of combining HLA-E or NKG2A editing and RIG-I stimulation was most
399 readily observable at very low effector:target (E:T) ratios (Fig. 3a-d, Fig. 5). Although many studies
400 use E:T ratios of up to 20:1 or 100:1 to assess target cell killing[118,119], the E:T in the tumor milieu
401 in tumors with high NK-cell density has been estimated at 1:35[120], and NK-cell based therapies,
402 even in combination with focused innate immune stimulation cannot be expected to raise E:T ratios
403 to the supraphysiological levels used in *in vitro* 2D culture. In line with this, we observed an
404 exceptionally robust increase in NK cytotoxicity in a liver cholangiocarcinoma model (Fig. 5e-h),
405 where E:T within the tissue were likely quite low. As a result, we also see great promise for
406 combining NKG2A-editing, CAR expression and RIG-I activation in the therapy of solid tumor entities,
407 particularly in combination with tissue-targeted RIG-I activation, e.g. using light-activatable
408 photocaging methods[121].

409 In order to efficiently edit NKG2A in primary NK cells, we developed a 2-guide approach (Fig. 4c),
410 which lead to defined deletions (here of 52bp) in primary NK cells (Fig. 4b, c). Other studies have also
411 developed paired-guide approaches, e.g. for library screenings of immortalized cells[91,122,123]. To
412 our knowledge, our study is the first to demonstrate the robustness and efficiency of dual guide
413 editing in NK cells, and this approach can equally be applied to NK-cell editing platforms in basic or
414 translational research. With efficient NK-cell genome editing, it is also conceivable to develop NK-cell
415 products devoid of multiple inhibitory receptors, depending on the indication. Moreover, due to the

416 high overall efficiency of our approach, we were able to use NKG2A-edited cells without an additional
417 sorting step. Sorting approaches to purify *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK cells have been used in multiple studies to
418 date[23,28,29]. However, only one study [23] actually evaluated the effect of sorting a relatively pure
419 NKG2A-negative population after gene editing and observed that it did not improve cytotoxicity.
420 Here, it is important to note that sorting by flow cytometry cannot distinguish between *NKG2A*^{-/-} cells
421 and NK cells that simply do not express NKG2A due to their phenotypic state. The correlation of
422 NKG2A expression and NK cell phenotype is controversial in the literature, with NKG2A described as
423 correlating with both proliferative and antiviral capacity[124,125] and exhaustion[126] depending on
424 the context and entity investigated. However, the sustained, supraphysiological levels of IL-2 and IL-
425 15 and rapid expansion during the culture of NK cells for cell therapy and genome editing in this
426 study and others, greatly upregulate NKG2A levels[103,106,127] , and the significance of unedited
427 NKG2A-negative NK cell populations during expansion for cellular therapy remains unclear.
428 To date, studies utilizing *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK cells, while extremely valuable, used autologous
429 models[23,24] or human cell lines without considering KIR matching[29] . However, due to the ability
430 of RIG-I activation to robustly upregulate classical HLA-I molecules and MHC-I presentation as part of
431 the antiviral response[71,128], we systematically investigated whether KIR-matching or mismatching
432 could potentially influence the synergism between *NKG2A* editing and RIG-I activation (Fig. 6). Here,
433 we observed that the combination of *NKG2A*^{-/-} NK and RIG-I activation improved cytotoxicity
434 regardless of the KIR matching status. Nonetheless, we were surprised to observe, in general, how
435 little effect KIR matching had on NK-cytotoxicity at all. Interestingly, we observed that single
436 mismatches could be far more important for NK-cytotoxicity (Sup. Fig. 6e) and that these varied with
437 the entity investigated and their individual HLA-molecule expression[129,130] . There is little overall
438 literature systematically comparing KIR matches and mismatches for different tumor entities.
439 However, to some degree, our data is in line with reports of single-KIR superdonors[131,132], which
440 underscore the importance of specific, active KIRs. Further studies will be necessary to understand
441 the interplay of KIR mismatching and cytotoxicity. However, within the scope of our study, both were
442 compatible with our approach. Overall, our study demonstrates that combination of *NKG2A* editing

443 with RIG-I activation has great potential for improving a wide range of NK cell-based therapies
444 whether autologous or allogeneic, including off-the-shelf NK cell-based therapies. Future studies
445 combining this approach with CAR expression or potentially NK-cell engagers[2,3] may lend further
446 application to this promising approach.

447 **Methods**

448 **Cell Lines**

449 The HLA negative B-Lymphoblastoid cell line 721.221 was kindly provided by Prof. Dr. Carsten Watzl
450 (Leibniz Research Centre for Working Environment and Human Factors, IfADo, Dortmund, Germany),
451 and cultured in IMDM with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). The epidermoid carcinoma cell line A-431
452 was cultured in RPMI 1640 medium with 10% FBS. The lung adenocarcinoma cell line A549, the
453 pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cell line PANC-1, and HEK-Blue™ IFN α /b cells (Invivogen,
454 Toulouse, France) were cultured in DMEM with 10% FBS. The colorectal adenocarcinoma cell line
455 Caco-2 was cultured in DMEM with 20% FBS. The pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cell line Capan-2
456 was cultured in RPMI with 15% FBS. The ovarian serous cystadenocarcinoma cell line EFO-21 was
457 cultured in RPMI with 20% FBS, 2 mM L-glutamine (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Frankfurt am Main,
458 Germany), 1g MEM non-essential amino acids (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and 1 mM sodium pyruvate
459 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The colon adenocarcinoma cell line HT-29 and the choriocarcinoma cell
460 line JEG-3 were cultured in DMEM with 10% FBS, 1X MEM non-essential amino acids, and 1 mM
461 sodium pyruvate. The lymphoblast cell line K-562, and the ovarian adenocarcinoma line SK-OV-3
462 were cultured in RPMI 1640 with 10% FBS, 1X MEM non-essential amino acids, and 1 mM sodium
463 pyruvate. The osteosarcoma cell line U-2 OS was cultured in McCoy's 5A medium with 10% FBS. The
464 natural killer cell line NK-92 was cultured in alpha-MEM with 12.5% FBS, 12.5% horse serum (PAN-
465 Biotech), 2 mM L-Glutamine, and 100 U/ml IL2 (ImmunoTools, Friesoythe, Germany). All media were
466 supplemented with 100 U/ml Penicillin and 100 μ g/ml Streptomycin (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Cells
467 were cultured in a humidified incubator at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Unless otherwise stated, cells were
468 purchased from the Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures
469 GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany.

470 **Human Primary cell culture**

471 **NK cell isolation**

472 Human NK cells were isolated by immunomagnetic negative selection from whole blood from healthy
473 donors (aged 20 to 45 years, both sexes) with EasySep Direct Human NK Cell Isolation Kit (Stemcell
474 Technologies, Cologne, Germany) and cultured in NK MACS medium (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch
475 Gladbach, Germany) supplemented with 5% human AB serum (PAN-Biotech), and 1000 IU/ml
476 recombinant human IL-2 and 20 ng/ml IL-15 (ImmunoTools). All donor identities were anonymized.

477 **Liver Cholangiocarcinoma Organoid culture**

478 Fresh tumor pieces from surgical material were collected in washing medium (Advanced DMEM/F12
479 (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific) supplemented with 1x GlutaMax (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific), 10
480 mM HEPES (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 100 µg/mL Normocin (InvivoGen), and 2.5 µg/mL Amphotericin
481 B (Biowest, Nuaille, France) and placed at 4°C until processing. The adjacent tumor area was fresh-
482 frozen and microscopically investigated, to obtain pure tumor areas. Tumor samples were cut into
483 approximately 2mm³ pieces followed by further mechanical dissociation in 4 mL wash media using
484 GentleMACS C Tubes and a GentleMACS™ Octo Dissociator (both Miltenyi Biotec). Afterwards, the
485 resultant cell suspension was centrifuged (400g, 3 minutes) and RBC lysis was performed using Red
486 Blood Cell Lysing Buffer Hybri-Max™ (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis MI, USA) following the manufacturer's
487 instructions. The cell suspension was washed twice followed by resuspension in pre-prepared (on ice)
488 collagen mixture consisting of 8 parts Cellmatrix Type I-A (Fujifilm Wako Chemicals, Japan), 1-part 10x
489 Ham's F-12 nutrient mix (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and 1 part sterile-filtered reconstitution
490 buffer with 261.8 mM NaHCO₃ (Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany), 0.05 N NaOH (Merck, Darmstadt,
491 Germany), 200 mM HEPES (Carl Roth). The cell suspension was distributed as domes on a pre-warmed
492 6-well culture plate. Thereafter, the plate was incubated inverted in a cell culture incubator for 20
493 minutes to allow collagen solidification. Then, 1500 µL of organoid culture media was added per well
494 (a 1:1 ratio of L-WRN cells (ATCC, Virginia, USA) conditioned media and organoid basic media:
495 Advanced DMEM/F12 supplemented with 2% penicillin/streptomycin, 2x GlutaMax, 20 mM HEPES, 2x
496 B27 supplement (50x) without Vitamin A, 2x N2 supplement, 20 nM [Leu15]-Gastrin I human (Merck),

497 2.5 mM n-Acetyl-L-cysteine (Acros Organics, Thermo Fisher Scientific), 20 mM nicotinamide (Sigma-
498 Aldrich) supplemented with 50 ng/ml recombinant human EGF, 100 ng/ml recombinant human FGF10,
499 25 ng/ml recombinant human HGF (all three from Proteintech, Planegg, Germany), 10 μ M Forskolin
500 (Tocris, Bristol, UK), 5 μ M A8301 (Tocris), 10 μ M Y27632 dihydrochloride (Selleck Chemicals), 100
501 μ g/mL Normocin (InvivoGen). The protocol for the organoid culture media was adapted from (Broutier
502 et al., 2017; Huch et al., 2015)). Cultures were maintained in a humidified cell culture incubator (37°C,
503 5% CO₂) and culture media was replaced twice per week.

504 Organoid cultures were passaged at a 1:4 ratio once per week or whenever most organoids reached
505 \geq 100 μ m in diameter. For passaging, cultures were incubated with 1 mg/mL collagenase type 4
506 (Rockland Immunochemicals, Limerick, PA, USA) in wash media for 30 minutes at 37°C, then incubated
507 with 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 10 minutes at 37°C, followed by washing
508 in wash media supplemented with 10% FBS (Gibco™, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Thereafter, the cell
509 pellet was resuspended in pre-prepared collagen mixture and seeded as described above.

510 **Plasmids**

511 For protein overexpression, the human HLA-E CDS from cDNA obtained from K-562 (HLA-E 01:03) or
512 from EFO-21 (HLA-E 01:01) was cloned into a 3rd generation lentivector #1: pLenti6-EF1alpha-IRES-
513 EGFP (a derivative of Invitrogen pLenti6, kindly provided by Jonas Doerr, Institute of Reconstructive
514 Neurobiology, University of Bonn) or #2: pLenti6-EF1alpha-IRES-GFP-2A-Puro (derived from lentivector
515 #1) via Sall/NotI restriction sites (Primer sequences in Supplementary Table 3).

516 Human HLA-E deficient cells were generated by CRISPR-Cas9 mediated genome editing via transient
517 transfection of EF1a-Cas9-U6-sgRNA expression plasmids. SgRNA targets were selected with IDT's
518 CRISPR-Cas9 design tool and integrated into plasmids via Gibson assembly. Sequences are listed in
519 Supplementary Table 3.

520 **Lentivirus production and transduction**

521 Lentiviral particles were generated by calcium phosphate transfection as previously described[133] .
522 Briefly, 15x10⁶ 293FT cells were transfected with 40 μ g Lentiviral vector, 12 μ g psPAX2, and 6 μ g VSV-
523 G encoding plasmids with calcium phosphate protocols. Viral supernatants were concentrated by

524 ultracentrifugation at 26000 rpm for 3 h with a Beckman Coulter SW32-TI rotor. Viral pellets were
525 resuspended in OptiMEM and added to A-431, A549, SK-OV-3 and HT-29 cells. GFP-positive cells were
526 enriched by fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) (BD FacsAria III Sorter, Flow Cytometry Core
527 Facility Bonn).

528 **Generation of HLA-E deficient cell lines by CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing**

529 A549, SK-OV-3, A-431, EFO-21, and Caco-2 cells were electroporated with EF1a-Cas9-U6-sgRNA-2A-
530 EGFP plasmid coding for transient expression of Cas9 and gRNA targeting the HLA-E gene, using the
531 Neon Transfection System (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Electroporation parameters were 1200V, 30 ms,
532 and 2 pulses for A549 and A-431; 1170 V, 30 ms, and 2 pulses for SK-OV-3; 1400 V, 10 ms, and 4 pulses
533 for EFO-21; and 1600 V, 10 ms, 3 pulses for Caco-2. GFP-positive cells were sorted after 18 h and clones
534 were obtained by limiting dilution plating. After expansion, *HLA-E*^{-/-} clones were identified by Sanger
535 sequencing and confirmed by Immunoblotting. Genotypes are listed in Supplementary Table 1.

536 **CRISPR-Cas9 gene-editing of NKG2A in primary NK cells**

537 After 10 days in culture, NK cells were harvested and electroporated with Cas9 RNPs consisting of Alt-
538 R S.p HiFi Cas9 Nuclease, tracrRNA and either one or two XT-crRNA (IDT), using the Neon Transfection
539 System (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Briefly, cells were washed two times with PBS, resuspended in
540 electroporation Buffer T at 1x10⁸ cells/ml, and 10 µl were mixed with Cas9 RNPs consisting of 22 pmol
541 crRNA XT:tracrRNA duplex and 18 pmol Cas9 (pre-assembled for 15 minutes at RT), and 21.6 pmol Alt-
542 R Cas9 Electroporation Enhancer. The mix was electroplated with 2150 V, 15 ms, 2 pulses. HBSS
543 without calcium, magnesium, and Phenol Red was used as electrode buffer. Efficiency of polyclonal
544 NKG2A ablation was determined by Sanger sequencing and Flow cytometry.

545 ***In vitro* tumor cell stimulation**

546 The RIG-I ligand and control ligand (3p-dsRNA and 3p-ssRNA, respectively) were generated by in vitro
547 transcription with a TranscriptAid T7 in vitro transcription kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using annealed
548 DNA oligonucleotides as a dsDNA template (sequence for 3p-dsRNA:
549 TTGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGACGCTGACCCAGAAGATCTACTAGAAATAGTAGATCTTCTGGGTCAGCGT
550 CCC, sequence for 3p-ssRNA:

551 CGCGCGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGCGCAGACGCGAGCGCGGCACGGCCGCAAGGCGAGAC) as
552 previously described.[134]

553 For stimulations, 1.5×10^5 cells per well were plated in 1 ml of medium into 24 well plates and
554 stimulated on the following day. For lipofection, 1 μ g 3p-dsRNA, or HT-DNA (herring testes DNA, type
555 XIV, Sigma-Aldrich) were complexed with 2 μ l Lipofectamine 2000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according
556 to manufacturer's instructions. 1 μ g pl:C (Invivogen) was transfected with 3 μ l TransIT-LT1 (Mirus Bio),
557 or 10 μ g/ml pl:C was added directly to the medium for TLR3 activation. $INF\alpha$ and $INF\gamma$ (both purchased
558 from ImmunoTools) were used at 1000 IU/ml. Stimulations were prepared by duplicate in 100 μ l per
559 well and kept for the indicated times.

560 **RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis and qPCR**

561 RNA was isolated by lysing the cells from a 24-well in 350 μ l RLT buffer (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany),
562 mixing with 1 volume Ethanol 70% and loading into Zymo Spin IIIICG Columns (Zymo Research). RNA
563 was washed with 500 μ l RW1 (Qiagen) and two-times with 350 μ l RNA wash buffer (Zymo), dry-
564 centrifuged, and eluted with 30 μ l water (all centrifuge steps 12,000g/1min/RT except drying step 2
565 min). RNA was treated with DNase I (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and cDNA transcribed with RevertAid
566 Reverse Transcriptase (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and random hexamer primers (IDT, Leuven, Belgium).
567 qPCR was performed with EvaGreen qPCR Mix II (Bio-Budget Technologies) according to
568 manufacturer's instructions, and measurements were taken on a Quantstudio 5 384-well cycler
569 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Primers are listed on Supplementary Table 3.

570 **NK cell cytotoxicity assay**

571 NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity was analyzed by a flow cytometric lysis assay as previously
572 described[135] 100 μ L target cells with a concentration of 1×10^5 cells/mL were seeded in 96-well U-
573 bottom plates and incubated overnight. The medium was removed, and cells were stained with 300
574 pM DiO for 30 minutes in the dark at 37°C. After DiO removal from the target cells, the cells were
575 washed with complete medium, and 100 μ l of NK cell suspension, in the same medium as the target
576 cell is cultured, was added to the wells. NK cell concentration was adjusted so that the desired effector-
577 to-target ratio (E:T) was obtained: from 10:1 to 0.6:1 for NK92, and from 5:1 to 0.3:1 for primary NK

578 cells. As controls, every plate contained wells with only target cells (TA) and wells with NK cells alone.
579 Every condition was run in triplicate in all experiments. Plates were centrifuged for 2 minutes at 150 g
580 to increase cell contact and incubated for 20 h in an incubator. Subsequently, supernatants were
581 collected for IFN γ measurement by ELISA, and cells were detached with trypsin and stained for flow
582 cytometry with Zombie NIR viability dye (BioLegend, City, Country), and anti-CD45 (1:250) to
583 discriminate dead cells and targets from NK cells, respectively. Samples were washed with FACS buffer,
584 resuspended in 150 μ l FACS buffer per well, and measured with Attune NxT Flow Cytometer (Thermo
585 Fisher Scientific) using Invitrogen™ Attune™ NxT Software, and analyzed with FlowJo 10.10 (FlowJo
586 LLC, BD Biosciences). Specific lysis (%) was calculated as $100 * (\% \text{ cells alive in TA} - \% \text{ cells alive in Assay}$
587 $\text{Well}) / \% \text{ cells alive in TA}$.

588 For cocultures with suspension cells (K-562 and 721.221), the target cells were stained with 300 pM
589 DiO for 30 minutes, washed with complete medium and plated in 50 μ l/well (10000 cells/well). NK cell
590 concentration was adjusted to achieve the desired E:T ratio by adding 50 μ l NK cell suspension. To
591 distinguish between target and NK cells, the CD45 antibody was replaced by anti-CD56 during staining.

592 **Coculture with pre-stimulated target cells**

593 For pre-stimulation, target cells were seeded as described above. After over-night incubation the cells
594 were either transfected with 400 ng/ml 3p-ssRNA or 3p-dsRNA complexed with 1 μ l/ml Lipofectamine
595 2000 (according to manufacturer's instructions, in 25 μ l/well) for RIG-I stimulation or treated with or
596 without 1000 U/ml IFN γ (ImmunoTools). Cocultures were performed 24 h after stimulation and two
597 extra washing steps with PBS were applied before DiO staining.

598 When the cocultures were performed with pre-stimulated NK cells, the same stimulations were done
599 on the NK cells 24 h prior cocultivation with target cells. NK cells were washed 3 times with PBS,
600 counted and resuspended in the respective concentrations in the corresponding medium for the
601 cocultures.

602 To assess surface expression of HLA-E or NKG2A, the corresponding antibodies were added and stained
603 together with the CD56 before flow cytometry.

604 For NK cytotoxicity assays on tumor organoids, the cells were removed from the Matrigel with Cell
605 Recovery Solution (Corning Inc.), and organoids (equivalent of 5000 cells) were plated per well in 96-
606 well U-bottom plates pretreated with Poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate). On the following day, the
607 organoids were stimulated with 400 ng/ml 3p-ssRNA or 3p-dsRNA complexed with 1 µl/ml
608 Lipofectamine 2000 (according to manufacturer's instructions, in 25 µl/well). After 24 h of stimulation,
609 the organoids were collected, mixed by condition (RIG-I stimulated or CTR RNA stimulated), washed 2
610 times with PBS, stained with DiO and replated for cocultures. To do so, an aliquot was disaggregated
611 into single cells, and the equivalent volume of the organoid suspension containing 5000 cells, was
612 plated by triplicate in NK medium, and cocultured with NK cells for 24 h. After cocultures, Organoids
613 were dissociated into single cells with trypsin and pipetting, and cells were stained and flow cytometry
614 analysis performed to assess specific lysis as previously described.

615 **KIR and HLA-I genotyping of NK cell donors**

616 To determine whether primary NK cells express matching or mismatching KIRs for the ligands
617 expressed on the target cells A549, Capan-2 and A-431, genomic DNA was isolated from 10 ml of donor
618 blood using QIAmp DNA Blood Maxi Kit (Qiagen, Tilde, Germany), following the manufacturer's
619 instructions. The KIR present in the genome of the donors was determined by primer-specific PCR with
620 a KIR typing Kit (Miltenyi Biotec) and evaluated by gel electrophoresis.

621 HLA class I (HLA-A, HLA-C, HLA-B) genotyping of the donors was performed using the AllType™
622 FASTplex™ NGS Assay kits (One Lambda, A Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's
623 instructions. DNA sequencing library was sequenced on a MiniSeq DNA sequencer (Illumina Inc., San
624 Diego, CA). Data analysis was performed using the TypeStream Visual software (One Lambda).

625 **Flow cytometry analysis of stimulated target cells**

626 For analysis of HLA-E and HLA-A/B/C on tumor cells, the cells were detached, or directly resuspended
627 in PBS (Gibco), and stained on ice with 1:4000 Fixable Viability Dye eFluor 780 (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
628 in PBS for 8 minutes. Cells were then split into 2 wells to stain either for intracellular or surface markers.
629 For surface, directly labelled antibodies (PE anti-human HLA-E [1:200, 3D12, BioLegend] and FITC anti-
630 human HLA-A, B, C were diluted in flow buffer (PBS 2% FBS, 2mM EDTA, and 0.01% sodium azide). For

631 intracellular staining, the cells were fixed with 1 % paraformaldehyde (Carl Roth) in PBS for 1 h at RT,
632 and permeabilized with 0.5 % saponin (Carl Roth) in flow buffer (perm. Buffer). Permeabilized cells
633 were stained intracellularly with PE/Cy7 anti-human HLA-E and Brilliant Violet 510 anti-human HLA-A,
634 B, C for 1 h in perm. Buffer. Samples were measured with Attune NxT Flow Cytometer (Thermo Fisher
635 Scientific) using Invitrogen™ Attune™ NxT Software, and analyses with FlowJo 10.10 (FlowJo LLC, BD
636 Biosciences).

637 **Primary NK cell characterization by flow cytometry**

638 To characterize NK cells by flow cytometry, they were cocultured for 4 h with 721.221 at E:T 1:1. Briefly,
639 1×10^5 target cells were plated per well and 1×10^5 NK cells were added on top. Control wells were added
640 with only NK and only target cells. The final volume was of 100 μ l/well in 96-U-bottom plates. For
641 degranulation assays, anti-CD107a antibody was added to the medium at the beginning of the
642 cocultures (4 h in total). When cytokines were stained intracellularly, Brefeldin A (5 μ g/ml, BioLegend)
643 and Monensin (2 μ M, BioLegend) were added to the cocultures for the last 3 h of culture.

644 Cells were stained on ice with 1:4000 Fixable Viability Dye eFluor 780 in PBS for 8 minutes, followed
645 by surface staining of markers in flow buffer with directly labeled antibodies (Supplementary Table 4).
646 For intracellular staining, the cells were fixed and permeabilized as described before and stained in
647 permeabilization buffer (antibodies and dilutions are listed in Supplementary Table 4).

648 **Immunoblotting**

649 For immunoblotting analysis, 1 million cells were lysed in 100 μ l Laemmli Buffer (120 mM Tris pH 6.8,
650 4% (w/v) SDS, 20% (v/v) glycerol, 5% b-mercaptoethanol, and 0.1% Orange G) and heated for 5 minutes
651 at 95°C. Cell lysates were separated on SDS-PAGE gels (12%) and transferred to nitrocellulose
652 membranes (Cytiva, Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany), blocked for 1 h at room temperature with 3%
653 milk in PBS and probed overnight with antibodies against HLA-E (MEM-E/02, Abcam), HLA-G (4H84,
654 Santa Cruz Biotechnology), and b-tubulin (9F3, Cell Signaling Technology) at 4°C. Blots were then
655 incubated with secondary antibodies: Donkey anti-rabbit IRDye 680RD (1:15000 in 1 % milk, LI-COR
656 Biosciences, Bad Homburg, Germany), and goat anti-rabbit IgG-HRP (1:3000 1 % milk, Bio-Rad). Blots
657 were recorded on an Odyssey FC Dual-Mode Imaging system (LI-COR Biosciences).

658 **Cytokine detection**

659 Human IFN γ was measured using half the volume and concentrations of antibodies from
660 recommended by the manufacturer's instructions with the Human IFN- γ ELISA Set (BD Biosciences).

661 **IFN Type I HEK-Blue Assay**

662 HEK-Blue IFN α /b cells (Invivogen) were used to assess the release of Type I interferons by stimulated
663 cancer cells. 50,000 HEK-Blue cells were plated in a 96-well F-bottom plate, in 90 μ l medium, and 10 μ l
664 of either sample (supernatant from stimulated cells) or standard (2-fold serial dilution of IFN α 2a
665 starting with 20,000 U/mL) were added and incubated for 24 h at 37°C, 5%CO $_2$ in humidified conditions.
666 To measure IFN-inducible embryonic alkaline phosphatase in the HEK Blue supernatant, 10 μ l of
667 supernatant were incubated at 37 °C with 60 μ l PNPP in TRIS buffer (pH=9.5) for 1 h. The reaction was
668 stopped by adding 30 μ l 0.1 M EDTA, and the optical density (OD) was measured at 405 nm using an
669 Epoch Microplate Reader (Agilent).

670 **Quantification and Statistical Analysis**

671 Sample number and statistics are described in the respective figure legends. Statistical analysis was
672 performed with GraphPad Prism 10.

673 **Ethics Statement**

674 Human blood specimens were obtained from healthy donors and tumor tissue sections from patients
675 after written informed consent. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committees of the
676 University Hospital Bonn (approval numbers 331/23-EP and EK417/17). The study was conducted in
677 accordance with the ICMJE recommendations for the conduct and reporting of biomedical research
678 and the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Conflicts of interest are disclosed accordingly.

679 **Materials Availability Statement**

680 Further information and request for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled
681 by the Lead Contacts, Eva Bartok (ebartok@uni-bonn.de) and Sofía Soler (soler@uni-bonn.de).
682 Materials will be made available via material transfer agreement (MTA).

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688 (GH).

689 **Conflict(s) of Interest**

690 MS reports a grant DFG (IRTG2168, 272482170) which is thematically relevant for the current study.
691 MS and GH are co-inventors on an issued patent (10196638) on synthetic RIG-I ligands. GH and TZ
692 are both co-inventors on a pending patents on further synthetic RIG-I ligands (EP 23 205 742.2 to GH
693 and EP 24153970.9 to GH and TZ). MS, GH, and TZ are all developing further synthetic RIG-I ligands.
694 NB: The RIG-I ligands used in the current study were generated by *in vitro* transcription and not with
695 the processes described in the patents mentioned above. However, the authors see the overall
696 relevance of RIG-I activation in the context of NK cell therapy could be perceived as a potential
697 conflict of interest.

698 **Author contributions**

699 S.So., G.H., and E.B. designed the study; S.So., R.S., J.B., R.B., R.K., S.Sch., and C.H. performed
700 experiments; S.So., B.P., and E.B. collected and analyzed data; B.P., R.H., M.S., M.I.T. and T.Z.
701 provided reagents; S.So., T.Z., and E.B. wrote the manuscript; R.H, K.S.R., J.O., M.S., L.K., M.I.T., T.Z.,
702 G.H., and E.B. gave technical support and conceptual advice.

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1060 **Figure Legends**

1061 **Figure 1. RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity differs between tumor cell targets.**

1062 (a) Schematic representation of NK cytotoxicity assay with RIG-I stimulation of target cells and gating
 1063 strategy used to determine % specific lysis. TA: control wells with only target cells, AW: Assay wells
 1064 with specific effector-to-target (E:T) ratio. (b, c) NK cytotoxicity after 20 h-coculture with Capan-2, A-
 1065 431, EFO-21, HT-29, and SK-OV-3 cells previously stimulated with RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or a control
 1066 RNA (3p-ssRNA). Cocultures with expanded primary NK cells (b, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least
 1067 5 NK donors at different E:T ratios are shown) or NK-92 cells (c, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least
 1068 4 independent experiments at different E:T ratios are shown). (d) Type I interferon (IFN-I) activity in
 1069 supernatants from wells with target cells alone in the cocultures, tested in HEK-Blue Reporter Cells,
 1070 expressed as IFN α 2a equivalent units (EqU, n=4). (e) RIG-I activity in tumor cell lines as measured by
 1071 IFN-I production (X = IFN-I not detected, check mark = IFN-I production) and NK cytotoxicity after RIG-
 1072 I stimulation on target cells is summarized on the table for all cell lines included in the study: =
 1073 represents no differences in NK cytotoxicity, for increases in specific lysis: (+) < 5 %, + 5-10 %, ++ 10-
 1074 20 %, +++ > 20 %, n.s. statistically not significant. Abbreviations: Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML),
 1075 Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC), Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), Colorectal Cancer (CRC),
 1076 Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC), Ovarian Serous Cystadenocarcinoma (OSCC), and
 1077 Osteogenic Sarcoma (OGS). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with
 1078 matched donors and Šídák's (b, c) post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

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1081 **Figure 2: The MHC-I molecule HLA-E is broadly upregulated by RIG-I stimulation.**

1082 (a) Log₂ of the mRNA fold-change from genes involved in protection from NK cell mediated
 1083 cytotoxicity were analyzed from three publicly available datasets of human tumor cells stimulated
 1084 with RIG-I ligands. (b) Total MHC-A/B/C staining by flow cytometry after 400 ng/ml 3p-ssRNA or 1000
 1085 U/ml IFN γ stimulation for the indicated times. Shown are mean and SEM of geometric mean (GM),
 1086 n=4. (c) Immunoblotting of HLA-G basal expression and the housekeeping β -tubulin on the cell lines
 1087 included in the study. (d) Heatmap of Δ Ct values (HLA-G - GAPDH) on A549, A-431, SK-OV-3, and JEG-
 1088 3 cells stimulated for 20 h with 1000 U/ml IFN γ , 400 ng/ml RIG-I ligand 3p-dsRNA or medium as
 1089 control. (e) Protein expression measured by immunoblotting for HLA-E and β -tubulin on all cell lines
 1090 included in the study. (f) Summary of the responses measured by qPCR of stimulated cell lines with
 1091 ligands for the indicated receptors from graphs in Sup. Fig. 2d. Signs indicate changes in expression
 1092 as calculated by $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ method, with medium as controls. CXCL10 and IFIT1: + $5 \leq 2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} < 50$, ++
 1093 $50 \leq 2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} < 500$, +++ $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} \geq 500$. HLA-E: X $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} < 2$, (+) $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} = 2$, + $2 < 2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} \leq 5$, ++ $5 < 2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} \leq 10$, +++ $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)} > 10$. n.d. = not determined. n.s = statistically not significant result. (g) Heatmap of Δ Ct values
 1094 (HLA-E - GAPDH) on cells stimulated with IFN γ , 3p-dsRNA or medium as control from Sup. Fig. 2d. (h)

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1096 Surface HLA-E staining by flow cytometry after 400 ng/ml 3p-ssRNA or 1000 U/ml IFN γ stimulation
1097 for the indicated times. Shown are mean and SEM of geometric mean (GM), n=4.
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1100 **Figure 3: HLA-E induction on tumor cells limits RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity.**

1101 (a-d) Primary NK and NK-92 cytotoxicity measured on WT cells and three HLA-E^{-/-} A-431, SK-OV-3, EFO-
1102 21, and Caco-2 cell lines at E:T ratio = 0.6:1. The target cells were previously stimulated with 0.4 μ g/ml
1103 RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA) as indicated in Fig. 1a. Shown are individual values
1104 and mean \pm SD from 4 (SK-OV-3 and Caco-2) and 6 donors (A-431 and EFO-21), or pooled data from at
1105 least 4 independent experiments with the NK-92 cells (b). The observed contribution to NK-cytotoxicity
1106 (c, d) was calculated as average for: HLA-E deletion (HLA-E^{-/-} - WT), RIG-I stimulation (WT 3p-dsRNA -
1107 WT 3p-ssRNA), and the potential, synergistic effect of combination ((HLA-E^{-/-} 3p-dsRNA - WT) - (HLA-E^{-/-}
1108 ⁻ WT) - (WT 3p-dsRNA - WT 3p-ssRNA)) normalized to 100% of the total cytotoxicity observed for the
1109 combination. (e, f) Twenty-hour NK cytotoxicity assay on A-431, SK-OV-3, and A549 WT and HLA-E^{-/-}
1110 cell lines previously stimulated with 1000 U/ml IFN γ for 24h or control medium at E:T ratio 5:1 and
1111 2.5:1 measured with primary NK cells (e, shown are the means of at least 4 individual donors and SD)
1112 or NK-92 (f, pooled data from at least 3 independent experiments). (g) Primary NK cytotoxicity on
1113 tumor cells transduced with lentiviral particles expressing HLA-E alleles 01:01, or 01:03, followed by
1114 IRES and GFP sequences (Lentivirus #1), or a lentivirus control expressing only GFP (EV). Statistical
1115 comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's (a, b, e, f) or
1116 Dunnett's (g) post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.
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1119 **Figure 4: Paired guide RNA CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing enables NKG2A deletion in primary NK**
1120 **cells.**

1121 (a) Schematic representation of the paired guide CRISPR system used to obtain NKG2A-deficient NK
1122 cells and the observed genome edits for the combined guides. (b) Genomic indels were quantified by
1123 TIDE after sanger sequencing of genomic DNA samples and are shown as percentage of the total reads.
1124 N.A. not assigned. (c) NKG2A expression was measured by flow cytometry 4 days after electroporation
1125 of primary NK cells with CRISPR-Cas9 RNPs containing gRNAs targeting NKG2A locus. Either one gRNA
1126 or a combination of two guides was used in the RNP complex formation (n= 6 or 7 donors \pm SD of the
1127 mean). (d) Protein expression levels of different NK-cell surface markers by flow cytometry one week
1128 after electroporation with -CTR or NKG2A RNPs (mean \pm SD from at least 6 donors is shown), and after
1129 4h coculture with 721.221 cells at E:T ratio =1:1(e). Shown is the mean of at least 6 donors \pm SD. (f)
1130 Flow cytometry-based cytotoxicity assay of primary NK cells after 20h coculture with A-431 (n=5
1131 donors) and Capan-2 (n = 4 donors) cell lines. (g) IFN γ was measured by ELISA from supernatants of
1132 cocultures of gene-edited primary NK cells with the indicated cell lines. (Shown is the mean of at least
1133 8 donors \pm SD.) Statistical comparisons were performed using a mixed-effects model with matched
1134 donors and Šídák's multiple comparisons test (c-e), or two-way ANOVA with matched donors and
1135 Šídák's post-hoc test (f, g). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.
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1137 **Figure 5: NKG2A-edited primary NK and NK-92 cells act synergistically with RIG-I stimulation to**
1138 **promote anti-tumor toxicity.**

1139 Primary NK cells were electroporated with RNPs containing two gRNA targeting NKG2A (NKG2Ag) or a
1140 control gRNA (-CTRg) and kept in culture for at least one week before assessing in vitro cytotoxicity in
1141 combination with target-cell RIG-I stimulation. Target cells were stimulated 24 h before cocultures with
1142 0.4 μ g/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA). (a) Specific lysis from primary NK cells is
1143 presented at different E:T ratios on Caco-2 (n=7 donors, mean \pm SD) and EFO-21 cells (n=5 donors,
1144 mean \pm SD). (b) The observed contribution to NK-cytotoxicity was calculated for the E:T ratio 2.5:1 as
1145 average for: NKG2A deletion (3p-ssRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTR NK), RIG-I stimulation (3p-dsRNA
1146 -CTR NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTR NK), and potential synergy in combination ((3p-dsRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA
1147 -CTR NK) - (3p-ssRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTR NK) - (3p-dsRNA -CTR NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTR NK))
1148 normalized to 100% of the increase (divided by the addition of all positive effects). (c, d) Specific lysis

1149 of Caco-2 and EFO-21 cells by NKG2A-edited NK-92 cells (c, n≥3 independent experiments) and
1150 observed contribution to NK cytotoxicity calculated as explained in b (d). (e-h) Primary intrahepatic
1151 cholangiocarcinoma (Liver CCC) derived organoids were characterized by immunohistochemistry
1152 against Cytokeratin 7 and CA19-9 (e) and used as model to measure NK-cytotoxicity. The organoids
1153 were treated with 0.4 µg/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA) for 24 h and cocultured
1154 with -CTRg and NKG2Ag electroporated NK cells for 24 h. Flow cytometry measurements of NKG2A on
1155 NK cells and HLA-E on target cells (f), and specific lysis (g, n=4 donors, mean ± SD) are shown. The
1156 contribution of RIG-I stimulation, NKG2A deletion, and the combination was calculated for E:T ratio
1157 2.5:1 (h). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and
1158 Šídák's post-hoc test (a, c, g), or paired t test for surface expression of NKG2A and HLA-E (f). *p < 0.05,
1159 ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

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1161 **Figure 6: Synergistic cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited NK cells and RIG-I stimulation is independent of**
1162 **donor/tumor KIR-matching.**

1163 (a) Schematic representation of the KIR-match and KIR-mismatch (KIR MM) definition used, and table
1164 of KIR and their ligands. Based on the NK-cell KIR expression and education status of the NK donors (if
1165 the ligand for the KIR is also present on the NK donor), and the HLA-I (KIR ligand) present in the target
1166 cells we defined 1. KIR Match: NK cells expressing all HLA-I present on the target and at least one KIR
1167 for each of the HLA-I ligands. 2. KIR MM: NK cells with at least 2 KIR/HLA-I combinations for which the
1168 ligands are absent on target cells. (b) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR match, or
1169 mismatch in the NK donor during 20 h cocultures with Capan-2 (n=5 donors with KIR match, and n=5
1170 donors with KIR MM) and A431 (n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=4 donors with KIR MM). (c)
1171 Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR matches or mismatches in the NK donor during
1172 20 h-cocultures with target cells previously stimulated with 0.4 µg/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or
1173 control RNA (3p-ssRNA). Capan-2, n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=5 donors with KIR MM. A-431,
1174 n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=4 donors with KIR MM. Statistical comparisons were performed
1175 using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's multiple comparisons test (b), or Tukey's post-
1176 hoc test (c). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

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